

Structural Assessment Based on Computational Models and Digital Twin Technologies

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Abstract

Modern structural design and assessment of aerospace and automotive structures relies on numerical modelling for the analysis of complex components under diverse loading conditions and material properties, reducing the reliance on costly experimental testing. However, these models often struggle to fully replicate the intricate real-world behavior of structures. Discrepancies arise due to factors like variable loading, environmental effects, material properties scatter, manufacturing imperfections, and other effects that can only fully observable in operation.

This paper explores the potential of digital twins to bridge this gap, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of structural assessments. As virtual replicas integrating numerical models with sensor data, operational history, and machine learning, digital twins offer a dynamic and comprehensive understanding of structural behavior throughout a structure's lifecycle. Approaches to enable model updating, real-time structural health monitoring, and the development of new methods for model calibration and validation that combine simulations with experimental data are proposed in this paper. This path can revolutionize design, evaluation, and maintenance processes, optimizing structures for performance and lightweight while upholding rigorous safety factors.

KEY WORDS: *aircraft structures, artificial intelligence, damage tolerance, digital twins, machine learning*

1. Introduction

Numerical modelling enabled the improved consideration of material properties and load spectra in aircraft design, namely in stress analysis and fatigue design. Once the design is done and validated, and aircraft are manufactured, subsequent analyses may be needed in several discrete moments along the plane's life. The long life foreseen for these structures is currently associated to the concept of limit of validity (LOV) [1], as defined by FAA [2] "The period of time (in flight cycles, flight hours, or both), up to which it has been demonstrated by test evidence, analysis and, if available, service experience and teardown inspection results of high-time airplanes, that widespread fatigue damage will not occur in the airplane structure". The many sources of uncertainty - as concerns loading, environmental effects, scatter of material properties and manufacturing variability -, instilled the interest for continuous assessments, for example through real time structural health monitoring (SHM) [3,4], leading to the adoption by the aeronautical community of the notion of digital twin. In IBM words [5], "A digital twin is a virtual representation of an object or system designed to reflect a physical object accurately. It spans the object's lifecycle, is updated from real-time data and uses simulation, machine learning and reasoning to help make decisions".

Digital twins may be seen to enable dynamic and comprehensive structural behaviour assessment throughout a structure's life cycle, improving the so far prevalent snapshot approach in discrete moments. The complexity of aircraft structures is indicated by the amount of documentation involved - at middle-age, a long-range aircraft amassed some three hundred thousand documents [6] -, indicating the need for a digital solution to take into account, in an useful way, the vast amounts of information involved. As virtual replicas integrating numerical models with sensor data, operational history, and machine learning, digital twins offer a solution for these needs, see e.g. [7-9]. The implementation of structural digital twins in aircraft engineering has high potential in various aspects of the industry, from design to end of life of a given aircraft family. These virtual replicas of physical aircraft structures offer numerous benefits across the entire lifecycle of an aircraft. Some of key applications of digital twins, considering the structural assessment, [10, 11] include:

- Design and product development improvements: structural digital twins support and improve design decisions, improving the accuracy of virtual models of aircraft components and systems. With data and information from the sensors and operations, the virtual models allow the simulation of multiple conditions with higher accuracy, allowing for rapid

iteration and optimization of designs. At the same time, these models also facilitate enhanced structural analysis with less physical testing, improving structural strength performance evaluation, and enabling more efficient material selection and weight optimization;

- **Manufacturing monitoring, control, and data gathering:** during the manufacturing process, digital twins can provide real-time monitoring of production processes and quality control through comparison of manufactured parts with digital models. These models also enable data collection for process optimization and defect prediction, as well as enhanced traceability of components and materials, essential for enhanced maintenance operations;

- **Assembly and quality assurance:** structural digital twins can help in ensuring precise alignment and fit of components during assembly operations. In this case, the digital twin can also help identify potential interference and tolerance issues before physical assembly occurs. These models also facilitate virtual assembly planning and optimization, improving quality control processes through comparison with digital reference models;

- **Operation, including operational envelope definition:** in operational contexts, digital twins may assist in defining and refining the safe operational envelope of the aircrafts. Based on real-time monitoring of structural health during flights and assessment of the impact of different flight conditions on structural integrity, structural assessment is more reliable. These models also support the definition of performance parameters based on structural constraints;

- **Maintenance:** currently, one of the most significant applications of structural digital twins is in predictive maintenance. Considering the capability of continuous structural health monitoring to predict potential failures and simulation of wear and fatigue over time, maintenance operations can be performed predictively and taking into account the specific data of a given aircraft. This leads to optimization of maintenance schedules based on actual usage and condition, ultimately reducing downtime through targeted maintenance interventions;

- **Lifecycle assessment:** throughout an aircraft's lifecycle, digital twins contribute to tracking and analysing the long-term performance of structural components. They assist in assessing the environmental impact of the aircraft over its lifespan and inform decisions on upgrades, retrofits, or retirement of aircraft. The data gathered through digital twins provides valuable insights for future aircraft design and development.

This communication aims to explore innovative concepts for digital twins, leveraging simulation models and integrating both real-world and experimental data. This data is obtained from laboratory analyses, such as material characterization, as well as from manufacturing processes and operational sensors. However, integrating data with simulations presents challenges, requiring advanced techniques to merge experimental data into simulations to calibrate and update the models throughout their lifecycle. With reliable and efficient digital twins, it will be possible to enable real-time structural health monitoring and enhance the damage tolerance design of aeronautical structures. The trend towards the future adoption of a digital twin philosophy has the potential to revolutionize design, evaluation, and maintenance processes, optimizing structures for performance and lightweight construction while maintaining rigorous safety standards.

2. Model Updating in Digital-Twin

Finite Element (FE) modelling is the most commonly employed technique for structural design and assessment, based on stress-strain calculation and failure modes under multiple loading and boundary conditions scenarios, guaranteeing the required safety levels. Due to multiple uncertainties, updating and calibration are critical in structural design. Updating and calibration aim at refining numerical models to better represent the behaviour of physical structures, catching unknown variables that were not considered in the initial calculations. FE model updating involves adjusting the parameters of a finite element model based on experimental data or field measurements, thereby reducing discrepancies between the predicted and observed responses of a structure. This process allows to improve the virtual model fidelity because initial finite element models, despite being based on theoretical principles and assumptions, often fall short in capturing the true complexities of real-world structures. This is due to factors such as material properties heterogeneity, uncertainties in loading and boundary conditions, and geometric inaccuracies, among other factors. Table 1 lists the most common scatter sources that contribute to the finite element inaccuracies and are particularly difficult to quantify.

Table 1

Scatter sources with impact on the finite element model accuracy (adapted from Pizzanelli et al. [12])

Scatter Sources	Qualitative Parameter	Quantitative Parameter
Manufacturing	Geometry deviations (including thicknesses) Assembly joints mismatch	Material and manufacturing processes associated: tolerances
Loads/mechanics	Environment Operational	Use of aircraft: loads/stress Geometry changes during lifecycle External/internal damages (including fatigue and ageing)
Test/experimental data (mechanical characterization)	Representativeness of tests (specimens+loads simplification) Analyses of experimental data	Number of specimens Scatter

Several techniques ranging from traditional methods to advanced computational algorithms have been proposed for updating and calibration in finite element method (FEM). Sensitivity-based updating is a conventional approach where model parameters are adjusted iteratively based on the sensitivity of the model's response to these parameters. Optimization algorithms, such as gradient-based methods and genetic algorithms, are also widely used to minimize the error between simulated and observed data. More recently, machine learning techniques, including artificial neural networks (ANNs), graph neural networks (GNNs) and Bayesian inference methods, have been integrated into FEM updating. These approaches leverage large datasets and probabilistic frameworks to enhance the model's predictive capability and robustness, accommodating uncertainties and variabilities inherent in real-world data.

FE model updating and calibration present multiple advantages, significantly impacting various fields of engineering and structures management in the transportation sector, with higher impact on airframes. By refining finite element models, higher accuracy in predicting structural responses under the diverse loading conditions are achieved, which is crucial for accurate digital twins, but also for the design, assessment, and maintenance of structures. Truthful digital twins enable the identification of potential weaknesses and the optimization of structural components, leading to safer and more cost-effective designs. Additionally, updated models' digital twins can provide a dynamic and comprehensive tool for ongoing monitoring, diagnostics, and decision-making throughout the structure's lifecycle. Ultimately, FEM updating, and calibration contribute to improve the damage tolerance approaches, extending the lifespan of structures, enhancing their performance, and ensuring their safety and reliability.

3. Physics-Informed Machine Learning

Modelling and forecasting the dynamics of multiphysics and multiscale systems presents persistent scientific challenges. Over the past fifty years, substantial advancements have been made in understanding multiscale physics across various applications by numerically solving partial differential equations (PDEs) using methods such as finite differences and finite elements. Additionally, solving inverse problems such as inferring material properties in functional materials and discovering missing physics in reactive transport is often prohibitively expensive and requires complex formulations, novel algorithms, and sophisticated computer codes. This is where observational data become crucial. With the potential deployment of over a trillion sensors in the next decade, including airborne, seaborne, and satellite remote sensing, a vast array of multi-fidelity observations will be available for exploration through data-driven methods [13].

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning approaches offer tools for automatically extracting features from the large amounts of multi-fidelity observational data. These methods can also help link these features with existing approximate models and utilize them to develop new predictive tools. However, many current ML approaches struggle to extract interpretable and valuable information from data. Furthermore, purely data-driven models may fit observations well, but their predictions might be physically inconsistent or implausible [13, 14]. Therefore, it is essential to integrate fundamental physical laws and domain knowledge by 'teaching' ML models the governing physical rules, providing strong theoretical constraints alongside observational ones. This necessity has given rise to physics-informed learning, defined as the process of leveraging prior knowledge from observational, empirical, physical, or mathematical understanding of the world to enhance the performance of learning algorithms. An emerging example of this new learning philosophy is the family of 'physics-informed neural networks' (PINNs) [15].

Fig. 1 illustrates three possible categories of physical problems based on the availability of data. In the small data regime, it is assumed that all the physics are known, and data are provided for the initial and boundary conditions, as well as the coefficients of a partial differential equation. In the middle regime, which is the most common in practical applications, the data and some physics are known. There is the possibility of missing some parameter values or even an entire term in the partial differential equation. Lastly, there is the regime with big data, where none of the physics are known, and a data-driven approach is likely the most effective, for example, using operator regression methods to discover new physics. Physics-informed machine learning can seamlessly integrate data with the governing physical laws, even when the models have partially missing physics, providing a unified approach to problem-solving.

Fig. 1 Data and physics scenarios

To implement PINNs efficiently, it is advantageous to build new algorithms based on the current ML libraries, such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, Keras and JAX. Table 2 summarizes several software libraries specifically designed for

physics-informed ML that have been developed and are contributing to the rapid development of the field.

Table 2
Major software libraries specifically designed for physics-informed machine learning

Software	Usage	Language	Backend
DeepXDE	Solver	Python	TensorFlow
SimNet	Solver	Python	TensorFlow
PyDens	Solver	Python	TensorFlow
NeuroDiffEq	Solver	Python	PyTorch
NeuralPDE	Solver	Julia	Julia
NVIDIA Modulus	Solver	Python	PyTorch
SciANN	Wrapper	Python	TensorFlow
ADCME	Wrapper	Julia	TensorFlow
GPyTorch	Wrapper	Python	PyTorch
Neural Tangents	Wrapper	Python	JAX

Despite the recent advancements and successful applications of physics-informed learning, challenges persist, particularly in addressing multiscale and multiphysics problems. One notable issue is the difficulty that fully connected neural networks face in learning high-frequency functions, a phenomenon known in the literature as the 'F-principle' [16]. This principle indicates that neural networks tend to learn low-frequency components of a function much faster than high-frequency components, which can be problematic for accurately capturing complex, high-frequency behaviors in multiphysics systems.

Implementing physics-informed ML in digital twins offers several advantages such as [17]:

- *Better predictive accuracy*: Integrating physical laws directly into the learning process ensures that the models are not only data-driven but also adhere to fundamental physical principles, leading to more reliable and consistent predictions.
- *Real-time simulation*: The integration of physics-informed ML enables real-time simulations within digital twins. This is crucial for applications requiring immediate responses, such as industrial automation, healthcare monitoring, and autonomous systems.
- *Solving inverse problems*: physics-informed ML is particularly effective in solving inverse problems, which involve inferring system states or parameters from observed data. This capability is crucial for digital twins that need to diagnose issues and optimize performance based on sensor data.
- *Flexibility and adaptability*: physics-informed ML offers flexibility in modelling complex systems with high-dimensional inputs and outputs. They can easily adapt to new data and changing conditions, making them suitable for dynamic environments where digital twins need to continuously learn and update their models.
- *Reduced computational costs*: Compared to traditional numerical methods, PINNs can reduce computational costs by providing mesh-free solutions. This efficiency allows digital twins to operate more economically, especially in large-scale applications involving complex geometries and boundary conditions.

Physics-informed ML is well placed to become an enabling catalyst in the emerging era of digital twins thanks to its natural capability of merging physical models and data as well as the use of automatic differentiation that removes the need for mesh generation.

4. Examples

Firstly, the classical case of the plate subjected to uniform remote tensile stress, containing a central circular hole, is presented. The plate length and width are 500 mm and 250 mm. Due to symmetry, one quarter of the plate was analysed and the stress field determined considering plane stress. Uniaxial remote tensile stress acting parallel to the plate length. FEM results were obtained using Ansys and compared with results obtained using ML and ANNs. Fig. 2 shows the results for a circular hole radius of 50 mm. The case is treated in detail in Ribeiro [18].

Fig. 2 Graphical comparison of the stress field in the length direction of the plate with central hole (MPa) [18]

Fig. 2 shows stress rather similar stress fields, both in terms of the stress values and their distribution over the plate. Nevertheless, greater irregularity in the contour limits is found in the map predicted by the ANNs.

Another example concerns the analysis of stress concentration in a simplified aircraft fuselage panel subjected to uniaxial (hoop) stress, available in NVIDIA Modulus Sym [19]. NVIDIA Modulus Sym is a deep learning framework that combines the power of physics and PDEs with AI to build more robust models for better analysis. Due to the variations of altitude of the flying aircraft, the fuselage panel is subjected to different values of hoop stress that cause fatigue damage accumulation. In this example the parameterized model was trained with PINNs and, taking into account the boundary conditions and dimensions presented in Fig. 3a), can predict the stress and displacement in the panel for different values of hoop stress. The 2 mm thick panel material is the classical aluminium alloy AA2024-T3, with $E = 73$ GPa and $\nu = 0.33$. The objective is to train a parameterized model with varying σ_{hoop} between 46 MPa and 56.5 MPa. Plane stress equations were considered in this case study. In this case, the PINN model is trained considering the mixed-variable formulation, as proposed by Rao et al., [20]. Fig. 3b) shows the NVIDIA Modulus Sym results for panel displacements and stress. This study shows that NVIDIA Modulus Sym and commercial solver results are in close agreement, with a difference of less than 5% in the maximum von Mises stress [21], that considering the stress field gradients in the stress concentration regions may be considered a good result.

Fig. 3 a) Geometry and boundary conditions of the simplified aircraft fuselage panel; b) Linear elasticity results for the aircraft fuselage panel example with $\sigma_{hoop} = 46$ MPa [21]

Although this model was only trained for different hoop stress levels, a more comprehensive model is being developed considering the different scatter sources, enabling a model with multiple inputs, which can be updated in real time, providing panel stress and displacement, through the integration of experimental data and FE data.

5. Conclusions

In this paper the potential of digital twins in enhancing structural assessments was explored with focus on aeronautical structures; the considerations may be extrapolated to other structures. The digital twin concept proposed in this article integrates advanced numerical models with real-time sensor data, operational history, and machine learning to provide a comprehensive assessment of structural behaviour throughout a structure's lifecycle. This approach addresses the limitations of traditional models, which often struggle to replicate the complex real-world behaviour of structures due to factors like variable loading and material property scatter.

By continuously updating virtual models with real-time data, digital twins enable better decision-making and risk management, enhancing safety and extending the operational lifespan of aircraft. They also facilitate proactive maintenance, performance optimization, and reduce reliance on costly physical prototypes by allowing for virtual experimentation with different materials and structural configurations. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, particularly physics-informed machine learning, further enhances predictive accuracy and system capabilities. However, further research is required in order to improve the current formulations and the need of extensive data sets to train these models.

In conclusion, the adoption of digital twin technology combined with artificial intelligence tools represents a significant advancement in transport structures. It can improve safety, performance, and cost-efficiency while reducing environmental impact. As this technology evolves, it will play a crucial role in shaping the future of aircraft design,

manufacturing, and maintenance, leading to smarter, safer, and more efficient aeronautical structures.

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